

A REFINED STUDY OF THE RAIL SHEAR TEST ON SANDWICH BEAMS

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SUMMARY : The present work is an experimental evidence of some parasitic effects that occur during the rail shear test carried out on sandwich beams. With a whole-field technique, it is shown that the steel plates bend during the test and that compressive/tensile strains occur near the free edges, leading to an early failure of the tested specimen.

KEYWORDS : rail shear test, experimental investigation, sandwich structures, whole-field measurements.

INTRODUCTION

Two tests are generally carried out for measuring both the transverse shear modulus and strength of sandwich beams: the bending and the rail shear tests. The bending tests are easy to perform but provide approximate values for the stiffness and strength. Another way for characterizing the shear response of sandwiches is to perform the rail shear test. The preparation of the specimen is somewhat more complicated than in the case of bending tests since the sandwich specimen since two steel plates have to be glued onto the beam [1], but the state of stress is expected to be more pure in this later case.

Several standards are available. They can be mainly distinguished by the design of the end grips which induce different loading conditions. An detailed comparison between these standard tests is available in Ref. [2].

Parasitic effects in the standard rail shear tests have been reported in the literature for a long time. They are mainly due to two phenomena. First, the steel plates onto which the composite skins are bonded bend during the test. Second, the shear stress is zero near the free edges. Consequently, a shear stress gradient takes place near them. This problem leads to an error in the displacement between the two steel plates which depends on the aspect ratio of the tested specimen [2]. It must however be emphasized that the local stresses near the free edges can be very different of the constant assumed ones, leading therefore to some local cracks in the core that can initiate the failure of the specimen.

Some limitations of this test carried out on composite plates have been presented in Refs [3] and [4]. To the knowledge of the authors, refined studies of the bending tests on sandwich beams have been seldom carried out [5]. The objective of the present study is to use a whole-field measurement technique to observe the mechanical response of a sandwich beam subjected to the ASTM rail shear test. The experimental set-up used is first presented. The displacement/strain fields are then studied and some parasitic effect are shown.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Two sandwich specimens were tested. Their dimensions are reported in Table 1 and Figure 1.

length l mm	width b mm	height h mm	thickness of the skins e mm
300	70	23.81	2

Table 1 Dimensions of the tested specimens

Fig.1 Notations

The faces were laminated plates made of woven-glass and external mat. The thickness of these fiberglass laminates was 2 mm. Their longitudinal modulus was 15 GPa. The core was a slab of PVC foam Divinycell H80 of low density : $d=80 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kg/m}^3$. It was assumed to be isotropic : $G \approx 30 \text{ MPa}$. The sandwich beam was bonded between the two steel plates with an epoxy glue Araldite 420 A/B used in aeronautical applications.

Whole-field measurements were performed on the lateral surface of the beam during the test. The so-called "grid method" was used for measuring both x - and y - displacement fields. This method and a special software "Frangyne" that extracts the displacement fields from the measurements were developed by Surrel and co-workers [6]. Two grids have been bonded onto the lateral surface of the specimens. The first one (pitch=0.610 mm) is bonded on the whole surface. The second one (pitch=0.125 mm) is bonded near the free edge only to investigate more precisely the displacement/strain field in this part of the specimen. The principle of the method is fully described in several recent papers ([7] for instance). The load was applied at a constant rate 0.8 mm/mm. As recommended by the ASTM standard, the displacement between the two steel plates was measured by inductive displacement transducers fixed at the middle of these plates (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2 Mechanical set-up

FINITE ELEMENT CALCULATIONS

The measurements were compared with the displacement/strain fields provided by finite element calculations carried out with the ANSYS 5.1 package. A static linear elastic analysis

was performed on a model of the specimen. Each steel plate was meshed with 1200 plane 82 eight-noded elements, each skin with 600 elements and the core with 2000 elements. The boundary conditions are the idealized boundary conditions of the ASTM standard: a point M_1 located at the right-hand side of the fixed steel plate is blocked and a displacement is imposed at a point M_2 located at the left-hand side of the moving steel plate (see Figure 3).

Fig. 3 Model of the specimen

The location of M_1 and M_2 is adjusted is such a way that the M_1M_2 line is the diagonal of the sandwich, as recommended by the ASTM standard. The displacement is imposed along the direction of the M_1M_2 line. Note that this calculation is carried out with the initial configuration of the specimen. Hence a possible rotation of the set-up during the test is not taken into account.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Displacement between the two steel plates

The displacement between the two steel plates is measured by the two inductive displacement transducers fixed on the steel plates.

The two specimens tested gave similar results, as reported in Table 2.

	specimen 1	specimen 2	supplier
shear modulus (MPa)	24.0	24.9	$\cong 30$
strength (MPa)	0.68	0.68	0.6/1

Table 2 Shear modulus and shear strength measured with the rail shear test

Several loadings were applied at low level beforehand and the repeatability of the measured displacement/strain fields was checked. A good linearity of the global shear strain/displacement curve was observed. The shear strain is here a global one since it is computed by dividing the relative displacement between the steel plates measured by the two sensors by the core thickness.

Displacement field along direction x

The displacement field provided by the whole-field technique was captured at different stages of the loading. The displacement contours measured by the system at $P=14300$ N with the 0.61 mm pitch grid and processed by the software are reported in Figure 4. This value of the loading corresponds to the end of the fairly linear response of the specimen. A second experiment was carried out with the second specimen and the displacement field was measured by the system with the 0.127 mm pitch grid in order to assess more precisely the displacement field near the free edge. The corresponding measured displacement field is also reported in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 Displacement field along direction x

Both experimental fields are compared with the displacement fields computed with the finite element model. The x -displacement clearly depends only on y . This result is in agreement with the results provided by the F. E. model. The refined measurements obtained with the 0.127 mm-grid do not show any x -displacement gradient. It was checked that both the average x -displacement and the displacement measured by the transducer were in very good agreement during the test.

Displacement field along direction y

Both measured and calculated y -displacement fields are reported in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Displacement field along direction y

They are very similar and approximately proportional to x . The magnitude of the y -displacement is lower than the magnitude of the x -displacement shown above. A displacement gradient is clearly visible near the free edge. This gradient is however too confined to be accurately measured with the 0.61 mm pitch grid. This is probably the reason why the magnitude of both measured and calculated displacements are different. The gradient is much more clearly visible with the 0.125 mm pitch grid.

A schematic view of the magnified steel plate displacement given by the FE model is plotted in Figure 6 to show the expected movement of the two steel plates.

Fig. 6 Schematic view of the steel plate bending

The y -displacement measured at the center line of the mobile steel plate, *i.e.* at $y=(d+e)/2$ is displayed in Figure 7-a alongside the corresponding displacements calculated with the F. E. model.

a- moving steel plate

b fixed steel plate

Fig. 7 Displacement field along direction y at the center line of the steel plates

A vertical shift between measured and calculated curves is clearly visible. It is due to an additional displacement of the steel plate fixing point along the y -direction probably caused by a misalignment of the testing device. The curvature of the moving steel plate is lower than that predicted by the F.E. model, showing that the actual bending of this plate is lower than

expected. The y -displacement measured at the center line of the mobile steel plate, *i.e.* at $y=(d+e)/2$ is reported in Figure 7b. Both experimental and calculated curves are very similar and show the same phenomenon: the plate rotates clockwise during the loading.

Longitudinal strain field along direction y

The longitudinal strain field along direction y is obtained by numerically differentiating the y -displacement field with a suitable algorithm [8]. It is displayed in Figure 8 with the corresponding calculated field.

Fig. 8 Longitudinal strain field ϵ_{yy}

Fig. 9 Magnified deformed mesh near the free edge

The displacement gradient at the free edge causes both tensile (zone (1)) and compressive (zone (2)) strain gradients. This phenomenon is confirmed by the results provided by the FE model, even though the magnitude of the strain is higher in this latter case. This result is in agreement with the above conclusion since it was observed that the relative displacement between the two steel plates was greater with the FE model near the free edge.

Magnified deformed mesh near the free edge is plotted in Figure 9. It clearly appears that the elements in zone (1) are subjected to tensile strains along direction y whereas the elements in zone (2) are subjected to compressive strains. It is clear that this tensile strain field may initiate a crack in the core and may then cause early failure of the specimen, as discussed below. Finally, compressive strains are visible at the center of the core in the experimental field. This result lends credence to the existence of bending in the steel moving plate, since it

was shown that the center lines of the steel plates move towards each other apart from near the free edge.

Shear strain field

The shear strain field $\gamma_{xy} = 2\varepsilon_{xy}$ is obtained by numerically differentiating both the x and y -displacement fields with a suitable algorithm [8,9]. It is displayed in Figure 10 with the corresponding calculated field.

Fig. 10 Shear strain field γ_{xy}

The shear strain is approximately uniform in the central part of the specimen, decreases suddenly and reaches zero at the free edge. The length of the region where the shear strain is not constant is about one half of the core thickness. Both experimental and calculated strain fields are in good agreement. It has also been checked that the global shear strain provided by the two sensors is in good agreement with the present shear strain measurements [10]

Final yielding of the specimen

At $P=14300\text{N}$, a small crack appears at the free edge, near the moving steel plate. This crack is certainly due to the transverse tensile stresses in zone (1) discussed above. This confirms the fact that the failure of the specimen is caused by local stress concentrations at the free edges. The crack does not propagate and the displacement increases while the loading remains about constant. A crushing of the core along the diagonal becomes visible while the displacement imposed to the moving steel plate increases. In conclusion, it clearly appears that the local phenomena near the free edge initiate the early failure of the specimen, as confirmed in Ref. [11] where three-point bending tests performed with a suitable procedure were shown to lead to higher values for the shear strength.

CONCLUSION

A refined analysis of the rail shear test on sandwich beams has been carried out. Some parasitic effects have been clearly highlighted: the shear strain is not pure in the core, the steel plates bend during the test and strain gradients have been measured near the free edges. These effects lead to a conservative estimate of the shear strength measured with this test.

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